

Research Article

An Evaluation of Rights-Based Education (RBE) Framework in the Philippine Basic Education Using Paulo Freire Critical Pedagogy as Philosophical Lens: Basis for Sound RBE Implementation

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Article History	Abstract
<p>Received: April 15, 2026 Accepted: May 06, 2026 Published: May 12, 2026</p>	<p>This mixed quantitative and qualitative research evaluated the rights-based education (RBE) framework in the Philippine basic education using Paulo Freire critical pedagogy as philosophical lens. The study aimed to determine the RBE implementation based on the pedagogical approaches of Freire, which further aimed to develop a plan for sound RBE implementation according to the mandate of the department as stipulated in DepEd Order 31, s. 2022. Using validated survey questionnaires and interview protocol, students, teachers and guidance advocates provided the necessary data. Findings showed that the RBE framework implementation in public SHS in the Division of Biñan City was “moderately implemented”, supported by participants’ claim that they were not very familiar with RBE framework. The “rights to” education such as access to quality education based on Freire critical pedagogy was “moderately evident”, which indicated that Freire’s Pedagogy of Freedom was observed. The “rights in” education such as promotion of learner’s well-being based on Freire critical pedagogy was “moderately observable”. Teaching strategies employed by teachers and school programs/activities promote learners’ well-being. On Freire critical pedagogy, this sounds positive because the forms of education and teachers were necessary in affirming the “humanization”, which drives learners to become fully human free from any forms of oppression. It was concluded that there was no significant difference between the RBE framework implementation and Paulo Freire critical pedagogy in achieving the “rights to” education, but there was a significant difference in achieving the “rights in” education.</p> <p>Keywords: Rights-Based Education, Pedagogy of the Oppressed, Child Protection Policy.</p>

Introduction

Pursuant to DepEd Order 31, s. 2022 or child rights policy: adopting the rights-based education framework in Philippine basic education, DepEd and other stakeholders are mandated to respect, fulfill, and promote all children’s “rights to” and “rights in” education. As stipulated in the same DepEd Order, this framework is based on the tenet that each human being, by virtue of being human, is a holder of rights. The “rights to” and the “rights in” education are highlighted in this department order. First, by the “right to” education, it is expected that the two dimensions of children’s rights, i.e., the right to access education and the right to quality education, are promoted in all educational institutions. Second, by the “right in” education, it is likewise expected that children are respected, and their well-being is promoted in the learning environment. If these rights are protected and promoted, the department of education’s agenda of setting the new direction in resolving basic education challenges through “DepEd MATATAG” could be realized. The “right to” quality education of all facilities be promoted through, first, a relevant curriculum that aims to produce competent and job-ready as well as active and responsible citizens; second, through responsively improved basic education facilities; and

third, through support given to teachers so that they can teach better. The “right in” education can be promoted through school practices that ensure good care for learners and promoting learner well-being.

Another DepEd Order highlighting the improvement of access to, and the delivery and quality of basic education is DO 24, s. 2022 or the adoption of the basic education development plan 2030. The basic education development plan (BEDP) serves as a strategic roadmap for the department to achieve this improvement. As stipulated in this DO 24, s. 2022, the BEDP integrates rights-based education in the Department of Education (RBE-DepEd) which aims to provide DepEd and other stakeholders with guides on how to educate and nurture happy, well-rounded, and smart learners who enjoy their rights in school. With these guides, teachers will become aware of their duties and responsibilities to aspire to the holistic development of their learners which does not only focus on the intellectual training but also on education that promotes their well-being.

In this research, Paulo Freire’s critical pedagogy was used as philosophical lens to evaluate whether the rights-based education (RBE) framework in the Philippine basic education was observed and implemented by DepEd schools and other stakeholders. Paulo Freire (1921-1997), a Brazilian educator had enormously influential ideas on the role of education in the development of knowledge among learners. In his book, *The Pedagogy of the Oppressed*, Freire (2005), stated his invigorating critique of the dominant banking model of education. In chapter II of his book, *Pedagogy of the Oppressed*, Freire considered “banking” concept of education as an instrument of oppressions. He proposed a new way of educating the learners through a dialogical approach, that is found in chapter III of the same book. Through dialogics, the essence of education as the practice of freedom, Freire expects learners to become active agents in their own education. He proposed that education must create “men and women who develop their power to perceive critically the way they exist in the world with which and in which they find themselves; they must come to see the world not as a static reality but as reality in the process of transformation”.

Pietersen (2022) in his article, *Engaging Paulo Freire on deliberative democracy: dialogical pedagogy, deliberation, and inclusion in a transformative higher education online education space*, narrated his idea of an effective education system. For him, this system is characterized by an environment where learners feel cared for, included, and can deliver critical dialogical input in their learnings on Learning Management Systems (LMS) platforms. How to do it is shown through delivering quality education where equal distribution of resources is accessible to all. Like the domain 3.3 of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) (see DepEd Order 42, s. 2017), diversity of learners, Pietersen (2022) suggested that the education system can be effective where there are trained teachers who could manage diversity and teach effectively. By doing so, it could foster success and could provide a safe and friendly environment for learners. Based on Pietersen and on the critical pedagogy of Freire, the quality education, therefore, in the philosophical lens of Paulo Freire shall be viewed as a form of self-development and not as a memory test. Learners shall realize that being knowledgeable and educated is tantamount to being powerful. Furthermore, the “right in” education where learners’ well-being is expected to be of great priority in the learning environment can be viewed in Freire’s theory of education particularly using his own lived experience as its philosophical lens. This likewise entails that teachers must be provided with proper training to ensure that quality education is provided according to the mandate of the department as stipulated in the PPST.

The researcher embarked on this study to evaluate the RBE framework, focused on learners’ “rights to” and “rights in” education. This study sought to determine whether basic education has already shifted to its traditional pedagogy of delivering instruction such as banking system to 21st-century skills that have to be developed through the teaching-learning process. Buckle (2024) defined 21st-century skills as referring to knowledge, life skills, career skills, habits, and traits. These skills are believed to be significantly valuable to safeguard learners’ success in hurdling the challenges of today’s world. From basic education to college and from workforce to adult life, these skills are necessarily of great importance for an individual to survive.

Specifically, this evaluative study utilized Paulo Freire’s critical pedagogy as its philosophical lens since Freire’s educational philosophy promotes skills that are necessary in this pressing and challenging time. Although the RBE framework includes all key stages in Philippine education, this study focused its evaluation on the observable indicators of its implementation in the senior high school providers in the City Division of Biñan. The researcher opted to delve into this key stage to concentrate on the effects and relevance of RBE in the curriculum for senior high school learners particularly making them competent and job ready as well as active and responsible citizens. Furthermore, a critical evaluation of this RBE framework could likewise determine concrete parameters to address the learning gaps due to pandemic-related disruptions, hence, responding positively to DepEd’s learning recovery plan which focuses on learning remediation and intervention,

professional development, health, safety, and wellness. Lastly, this study would promote advocacy to ensure that the teaching-learning process is anchored on the RBE framework motivating and encouraging every teacher to devise instructional strategies that offer quality education while simultaneously engaging learners with enriching experiences for the promotion of their rights and well-being. The result of this study would be disseminated through various modalities like virtual or in-person and through different training platforms like FGD, SLAC, district and division conferences.

Material and Methods

The type of research design or methodology used in this study was mixed descriptive quantitative and qualitative. The descriptive quantitative method was used to obtain quantifiable data that involved numeric and statistical explanations using the validated researcher-made research questionnaire, while the descriptive qualitative method was used to obtain data that were described in detail using research tool like interview (Cornell *et al.*, 2014). The former's data were gathered, analyzed and interpreted using the most appropriate statistical tools, while the latter's data were gathered, analyzed and interpreted using thematic approach.

Likert scale was used in determining the level of RBE implementation, and the indicators of the "rights to" and "rights in" education based on Freire's critical pedagogy; while t-test was used to figure out the significant differences between the implementation of RBE framework and Paulo Freire critical pedagogy as perceived by teachers and students in terms of "rights to" and "rights in" education.

The respondents and participants of this study were public senior high school learners, teachers, and guidance advocates in the public senior high school providers in the Division of Biñan City for the school year 2023-2024. They came from six (6) public SHS providers namely: Biñan City Senior High School – Sto. Tomas Campus (Barangay Santo Tomas), Biñan City Senior High School – San Antonio Campus (Barangay San Antonio), Biñan City Senior High School – Timbao Campus (Barangay Timbao), Biñan City Senior High School – West Campus (Barangay Langkiwa), St. Francis National High School (Barangay San Francisco), and Biñan Integrated National High School (Barangay Santo Domingo). They were chosen as research respondents and participants because the concentration of this study's investigation was on this key learning stage.

The main instrument used in this study was survey questionnaire (quantitative) and interview questions (qualitative) made by the researcher and validated by experts in the department of education, SDO – Biñan City who were selected and requested to do the validation because of their expertise in the field where this study was related.

After the validation of the survey questionnaire, the instrument was floated on schools where this study was intended to conduct. The researcher sought approval from the Schools Division Superintendent and from the respective PSDSs of district where public SHS providers were situated. Their approval was used for the distribution of survey questionnaire and for the conduct of interviews.

The division memorandum with approved research as well as the regional memorandum with list of BERF grantees were presented to respective public SHS principals for the scheduling of the data collection. The validated and tested survey questionnaires were distributed to public SHS providers in the Division of Biñan City considering the number of participants.

The data were obtained from the retrieved survey instruments based on school heads' advice to ensure that "time-on-task" and "no disruption" of classes policy was observed. Though, some research participants gave a few minutes to answer interview questions. The frequency of responses was counted to determine the weighted average of each group as well as their overall rating for each research question. Afterwards, the most appropriate statistical tools were utilized for quantitative data collection, while thematic approach was utilized to interpret the qualitative data.

The respondents' perception on how RBE framework was implemented in public SHS providers in the Division of Biñan City was interpreted as follows: 4 – highly implemented, 3 – moderately implemented, 2 - poorly implemented, and 1 – not implemented. On the indicators that the rights to education such as access to quality education are achieved based on Freire critical pedagogy, the data provided by the respondents are interpreted as follows: 4 – very evident, 3 – moderately evident, 2 – poorly evident, and 1 – not evident. Lastly, the respondents' perception on the indicators that the rights in education such as promotion of learner's well-being are achieved based on Freire critical pedagogy is interpreted as follows: 4 – very observable, 3 moderately observable, 2 – poorly observable, and 1 – not observable.

Results and Discussion

The result of this study was based on the analysis, presentation and interpretation of the data gathered. There were two phases in the analysis, presentation and interpretation. The first part was based on the results of the questionnaires focusing on the quantitative analysis of data, and the second part was based on the results of the interview and focus group discussions focusing on the qualitative analysis of data.

Table 1. Student respondents' profile.

Gender			Grade level		
Male	Female	Total	Grade 11	Grade 12	Total
77	87	164	80	84	164
46.95%	53.05%	100.00%	48.78%	51.22%	100.00%

Table 1 shows that there were more female student-respondents than male student-respondents. There were only 77 or 46.95% of male respondents, while there were 87 or 53.05% female respondents. In terms of grade levels, most of them came from grade 12 with 84 or 51.22% respondents, while only 80 or 48.78% came from grade 11. The total student-respondents was 164. All of them were requested to answer the survey questionnaire to come up with the quantitative data, while only a few of them were asked to answer the interview questions to obtain the qualitative data.

Table 2. Teacher/guidance advocate respondents' profile.

Gender			Work experience			
Male	Female	Total	0-5	6-10	Above 10	Total
11	21	32	5	14	13	32
34.38%	65.63%	100.00%	15.63%	43.75%	40.63%	100.00%

Table 2 shows that there were more female teacher/guidance advocate-respondents than male teacher/guidance advocate-respondents. There were only 11 or 34.38% of male respondents, while there were 21 or 65.63% female respondents. In terms of work experience, most of them have been serving their profession for 6-10 years with 14 or 43.75%, followed by teacher/guidance advocate respondents who have been serving above 10 years already with 13 or 40.63%, while only 5 or 15.63% have been serving their profession from 0-5 years. The total teacher/guidance advocate respondents were 32. Similarly, not all these respondents were requested to answer the interview questions, nonetheless they all were all requested to answer the survey questionnaire.

Table 3 shows the perception on how RBE framework was implemented in public SHS providers in the Division of Biñan City as assessed by students and teachers/guidance advocate respondents. Two sets of indicators of RBE implementation were assessed in this area where the respondents were asked: "How is RBE framework implemented in public SHS providers in the Division of Biñan City?". First, the indicators of implementation under "rights to" education, while the second was under the "rights in" education. In general, there were nine items assessed under this area.

From the data gathered, the following results were obtained and shown in Table 3. Between the two sets of indicators, the "rights to" education was overall quite higher than the "rights in" education with 3.69 and 3.66 weighted mean respectively. Both were "Moderately Implemented" as shown in the data. In both indicators, students' weighted means were lower than teachers/guidance advocates. While teachers/guidance advocates rated "Learners' rights to education are promoted" as 3.75, students' rating in the statement "I receive and enjoy my rights to education" was only 3.63. Similarly, students' rating in the statement "I receive and enjoy my rights in education" was 3.60 which was lower than the teachers'/guidance advocates' rating of 3.70 in the statement "Learners' rights in education are promoted".

Under "rights to" education, item "I have access to education/Children's right to have access to education is promoted" had the highest overall weighted mean of 3.75; the students got a weighted mean of 3.78; while the teachers/guidance advocates, 3.72; thus, the perception on the RBE framework implementation in this item was interpreted as "Moderately Implemented".

Item "I receive quality education/ Children's right to receive quality education is promoted" obtained the second with overall weighted mean of 3.65, where students got weighted mean of 3.57 while teachers/guidance advocates got weighted mean of 3.72; thus, the perception on the RBE framework implementation in this item was still "Moderately Implemented".

Table 3. Perception on how RBE framework is implemented in public SHS providers in the Division of Biñan City as assessed by students and teachers/guidance advocate respondents.

Indicators of RBE implementation	Groups	Weighted mean	Verbal interpretation
I receive and enjoy my rights to education/learners' rights to education are promoted.	Student	3.63	Moderately implemented
	Teacher/GA	3.75	Moderately implemented
	Overall	3.69	Moderately implemented
I have access to education/children's right to have access to education is promoted.	Student	3.78	Moderately implemented
	Teacher/GA	3.72	Moderately implemented
	Overall	3.75	Moderately implemented
I receive quality education/children's right to receive quality education is promoted.	Student	3.57	Moderately implemented
	Teacher/GA	3.72	Moderately implemented
	Overall	3.65	Moderately implemented
I receive and enjoy my rights in education/learners' rights in education are promoted.	Student	3.60	Moderately implemented
	Teacher/GA	3.72	Moderately implemented
	Overall	3.66	Moderately implemented
I feel respected in school/children's rights are respected.	Student	3.46	Moderately implemented
	Teacher/GA	3.75	Moderately implemented
	Overall	3.61	Moderately implemented
My well-being is promoted in school/children's well-being is promoted.	Student	3.40	Moderately implemented
	Teacher/GA	3.75	Moderately implemented
	Overall	3.57	Moderately implemented
I am being developed to become competent and job ready as well as active and responsible citizens. The school implements a contextualized and relevant curriculum that could produce competent and job ready as well as active and responsible citizens.	Student	3.47	Moderately implemented
	Teacher/GA	3.81	Moderately implemented
	Overall	3.64	Moderately implemented
My school provides me with responsive and improved basic education facilities/the school ensures that it has responsive and improved basic education facilities.	Student	3.54	Moderately implemented
	Teacher/GA	3.69	Moderately implemented
	Overall	3.62	Moderately implemented
All school programs and activities ensure and promote my well-being/the school implements existing programs that support teachers to teach better.	Student	3.47	Moderately implemented
	Teacher/GA	3.69	Moderately implemented
	Overall	3.58	Moderately implemented

Under “rights in” education, item “I am being developed to become competent and job ready as well as active and responsible citizens. The school implements a contextualized and relevant curriculum that could produce competent and job ready as well as active and responsible citizens”, was the highest with an overall weighted mean of 3.64. Students’ weighted mean was 3.47 while teachers/guidance advocates’ weighted mean was 3.81. The second in rank was item “My school provides me with responsive and improved basic education facilities/The school ensures that it has responsive and improved basic education facilities”, with an overall weighted mean of 3.62 in which students obtained 3.54, while teachers/guidance advocates obtained 3.69. Third in rank was item “I feel respected in school/ Children’s rights are respected” with an overall weighted mean of 3.61. The weighted mean of teachers/guidance advocates was higher than the students’ weighted mean which were 3.75 and 3.46 respectively. Fourth was item “All school programs and activities ensure and promote my well-being/ The school implements existing programs that support teachers to teach better”. It obtained an overall weighted mean of 3.58 where teachers/guidance advocate was higher than students with 3.69 and 3.47 respectively. Lastly, item “My well-being is promoted in school” obtained the lowest overall weighted mean of 3.57 where students got 3.40, while teachers/guidance advocates got 3.75. Overall, all items in the indicators of RBE framework implementation were “Moderately Implemented”.

As stipulated in DepEd Order 31, s. 2022, the three dimensions of RBE-DepEd, namely, the right to access education, the right to quality education, and the right to respect and well-being in the learning environment are indispensable, interrelated, and interdependent with each other. The results showed that SHS providers in the Division of Biñan adhered to RBE-DepEd framework, however, necessary actions at the school levels may still be conducted to achieve its full implementation. This was shown specifically by their perception that access to education is promoted, which got the highest weighted mean from both groups. However, issues on providing quality education may also be considered, although it was ranked second among the indicators, the fact that students’ response was lower than the perceptions of the teachers/guidance advocates, there is a call to assess areas where the delivery of quality education has to be improved. This result was aligned with the Domain 3.3 of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers or PPST, stipulated in DepEd Order 42, s. 2017 and Pietersen (2022) which suggested that education system can be effective where there are trained teachers who could manage diversity and teach effectively. While the SHS providers adhered to their mandate of making their learners competent and job ready as well as active and responsible citizens, which got the highest weighted mean in “rights in” education, aspects on how to promote the well-being of students may also be considered because as shown in the results, it was the lowest among the indicators. This was also aligned with the idea of Pietersen (2022) and Freire’s critical pedagogy which stated that quality education should be viewed as a form of self-development and not as a memory test. Learners should realize that being knowledgeable and educated is tantamount to being powerful. Making learners competent and job ready confirmed the ideas of Buckle (2024) when he defined 21st century skills as referring to knowledge, life skills, career skills, habits, and traits which were believed to be significantly valuable to safeguard learners’ success in hurdling the challenges of today’s world and making them prepared for the world of work.

Table 4 shows the perception on the indicators that the “rights to” education such as access to quality education were achieved based on Freire critical pedagogy as assessed by students and teachers/guidance advocate respondents. Seven items were assessed under this area where the respondents were asked: “What are the indicators that the rights to education such as access to quality education are achieved based on Freire critical pedagogy?”

From the data, the following results were obtained and shown in Table 4. Item “The essence of education based on freedom is observed in your school” had the highest overall weighted mean of 3.57; the students got a weighted mean of 3.51; while the teachers/guidance advocates, 3.64; thus, the perception on the indicators that the rights to education such as access to quality education are achieved based on Freire critical pedagogy as assessed by students and teachers/guidance advocate respondents of this item was interpreted as “moderately evident”.

Item “Quality education is viewed as a form of self-development and not as a memory test”, got the second with an overall weighted mean of 3.53 where students got 3.51 while teachers/guidance advocates got 3.56. Item “Learners realize that being knowledgeable and educated is tantamount to being powerful”, obtained third having an overall weighted mean of 3.46. Students’ weighted mean was 3.59 which is higher than the weighted mean obtained by teachers/guidance advocates which was 3.33. Fourth item was “Learners see the world not as a static reality but as reality in the process of transformation”. It had 3.40 overall weighted mean with 3.47 for students and 3.34 for teachers/guidance advocates. “Learners develop their power to perceive critically the way they exist in the world with which and in which they find themselves” was the fifth item having an

overall weighted mean of 3.38 where 3.41 was obtained by students, and 3.36 was obtained by teachers/guidance advocates. “Learners are becoming active agents in their own education” was the sixth item with 3.37 overall weighted mean where students obtained 3.39 and teachers/guidance advocates obtained weighted mean of 3.36. Lastly, item “Banking system in education is still practiced in your school” obtained the lowest overall weighted mean of 3.14 where students got 3.17, while teachers/guidance advocates got 3.11, although it was still interpreted that the indicators that the rights to education such as access to quality education are achieved based on Freire critical pedagogy of this item was “moderately evident”.

Freire (2000), in his book, *Pedagogy of Freedom, Ethics, Democracy and Civic Courage*, mentioned two subjects such as the question of what forms education and becoming a teacher, and a reflection on progressive education. In Freire’s lens, “there is no teaching without learning”. As shown on the results of this study, the SHS providers in the Division of Biñan City conformed to the pedagogy proposed by Paulo Freire. Item “The essence of education based on freedom is observed in your school”, which got the highest overall weighted mean indicates that what Freire introduced as form of education favors the autonomy of the learners. It was consistent with the second item which states that “Quality education is viewed as a form of self-development and not as a memory test”. This was the educational practice that Freire proposed in his *Pedagogy of Freedom*, where learners must become active agents in their own education and not just recipients of information. In his book, *Pedagogy of the Oppressed*, Freire proposed a new way of educating the learners through a dialogical approach which was supported by the results of this study. In this sense, the learners were created, through education, as men and women who developed their power to perceive critically the way they exist in the world where transformation process occurs.

Another notable result was the item “Banking system in education is still practiced in your school” which got the lowest overall mean which indicates that there had been changes in the educative process in terms of assessment, and for Freire that is a good indicator. However, although the results showed positive in the lens of Freire, it is still necessary that schools must investigate the possible means to further improve their delivery of quality education because the overall indicator was “moderately evident”. This pressed the aim of this study to promote advocacy to ensure that the teaching-learning process should be anchored on the RBE framework that motivates and encourages every teacher to devise instructional strategies that offer quality education while simultaneously engaging learners with enriching experiences for the promotion of their rights and well-being.

Table 4. Perception on the indicators that the rights to education such as access to quality education is achieved based on Freire critical pedagogy as assessed by students and teachers/guidance advocate respondents.

Indicators of RBE, rights to education, through Freire critical pedagogy	Groups	Weighted mean	Verbal interpretation
Banking system in education is still practiced in your school	Student	3.17	Moderately evident
	Teacher/GA	3.11	Moderately evident
	Overall	3.14	Moderately evident
The essence of education based on freedom is observed in your school.	Student	3.51	Moderately evident
	Teacher/GA	3.64	Moderately evident
	Overall	3.57	Moderately evident
Learners are becoming active agents in their own education.	Student	3.39	Moderately evident
	Teacher/GA	3.36	Moderately evident
	Overall	3.37	Moderately evident
Learners develop their power to perceive critically the way they exist in the world with which and in which they find themselves.	Student	3.41	Moderately evident
	Teacher/GA	3.36	Moderately evident
	Overall	3.38	Moderately evident
Learners see the world not as a static reality but as reality in the process of transformation.	Student	3.47	Moderately evident
	Teacher/GA	3.34	Moderately evident
	Overall	3.40	Moderately evident
Quality education is viewed as a form of self-development and not as a memory test.	Student	3.51	Moderately evident
	Teacher/GA	3.56	Moderately evident
	Overall	3.53	Moderately evident
Learners realize that being knowledgeable and educated is tantamount to being powerful	Student	3.59	Moderately evident
	Teacher/GA	3.33	Moderately evident
	Overall	3.46	Moderately evident

Table 5. Perception on the indicators that the rights in education such as promotion of learner’s well-being is achieved based on Freire critical pedagogy as assessed by students and teachers/guidance advocate respondents.

Indicators of RBE, rights in education, through Freire critical pedagogy	Groups	Weighted mean	Verbal interpretation
All school programs and activities ensure my good care and promote my well-being.	Student	3.51	Moderately observable
	Teacher/GA	3.83	Moderately observable
	Overall	3.67	Moderately observable
I am provided with an equitable opportunity to improve myself/all learners are provided with equitable opportunity to improve themselves.	Student	3.51	Moderately observable
	Teacher/GA	3.80	Moderately observable
	Overall	3.66	Moderately observable
Teaching strategies promote my well-being.	Student	3.53	Moderately observable
	Teacher/GA	3.81	Moderately observable
	Overall	3.67	Moderately observable
I feel safe inside the classroom and within the school/ learners feel safe inside the classroom and within the school.	Student	3.44	Moderately observable
	Teacher/GA	3.81	Moderately observable
	Overall	3.62	Moderately observable
I am motivated to engage in activities that promote my well-being/learners are motivated to engage in activities that promote their well-being.	Student	3.46	Moderately observable
	Teacher/GA	3.78	Moderately observable
	Overall	3.62	Moderately observable

Table 5 shows the perception on the indicators that the “rights in” education such as promotion of learner’s well-being were achieved based on Freire critical pedagogy as assessed by students and teachers/guidance advocate respondents. Five items were assessed under this area where the respondents were asked: “What are the indicators that the rights in education such as promotion of learner’s well-being are achieved based on Freire critical pedagogy?”

From the data, the following results were obtained and shown in Table 5. Items “All school programs and activities ensure my good care and promote my well-being” and “Teaching strategies promote my well-being” had the highest overall weighted mean of 3.67; the students got a weighted mean of 3.51 and 3.53 respectively; while the teachers/guidance advocates, 3.83 and 3.81 respectively; thus, the perception on the indicators that the rights in education such as promotion of learner’s well-being are achieved based on Freire critical pedagogy as assessed by students and teachers/guidance advocate respondents of this item was interpreted as “moderately observable”.

The second item was “I am provided with an equitable opportunity to improve myself/all learners are provided with equitable opportunity to improve themselves”, with an overall weighted mean of 3.66 in which students got 3.51 while teachers/guidance advocates got 3.80. On the other hand, items “I feel safe inside the classroom and within the school/ learners feel safe inside the classroom and within the school” and “I am motivated to engage in activities that promote my well-being/learners are motivated to engage in activities that promote their well-being” obtained the lowest overall weighted mean of 3.62 where students got 3.44 and 3.46 respectively, while teachers/guidance advocates got 3.81 and 3.78 respectively, although it was still interpreted that the indicators that the rights to education such as access to quality education are achieved based on Freire critical pedagogy of this item was “moderately observable”.

The results of this study on the indicators of RBE, rights in education, through Freire critical pedagogy adhered to the principles, strands and domains indicated in the DepEd Order 42, s. 2017 or National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). With the items “Teaching strategies promote my well-being” and “All school programs and activities ensure my good care and promote my well-being”, which got the highest overall weighted mean, the “rights in” education was “moderately observable”. PPST Domain 2: Learning environment stipulates the strands and the indicators whether teachers have been achieving them such as: strands 2.1 and 2.2 where “learner safety and security” and “fair learning environment” are promoted. This result was aligned with an article published by Malipot (2022) regarding DepEd’ Order to adopt the rights-based education (RBE) framework, which aimed to promote the holistic development of the learners. As stated in the article, it was only possible if basic education shows evidence of being child-centered and child-caring that is in accordance with the Department’s visions. Freire (2005), in his book, *The Pedagogy of the Oppressed*, mentioned “humankind’s central problem. He referred to

it as “humanization” and “dehumanization”. When man naturally manifests his drive to affirm himself as human being, then he is affirming “humanization”, however, when man cannot naturally manifest such drive due to factors such as oppression, then he is affirming “dehumanization”. From these ideas, Freire introduced that liberation from oppression is an important task of the people. Human beings as we are, we always confront with any forms of struggles to become ourselves, and those who hinder us in our becoming are the oppressors. Using the lens of Freire, the results of this study showed that SHS providers served as important agents for learners to promote “humanization”, as it was “moderately observable” that “Teaching strategies promote my well-being” and “All school programs and activities ensure my good care and promote my well-being”. Although, items “I feel safe inside the classroom and within the school” and “I am motivated to engaged in activities that promote my well-being” got the lowest overall weighted mean, they did not in any way deny that Freire’s ideas were contradicted. Both were still rated as “moderately observable” and just closer to other items’ ratings.

Table 6. A significant difference between the implementation of RBE framework and Paulo Freire critical pedagogy as perceived by teachers and students in terms of the indicators that the rights to and rights in education are achieved.

RBE framework	Groups	WM	T-test	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Indicators of RBE framework implementation	Students	3.55	4.320	.003	Reject H ₀	Significant
	Teachers/GA	3.73				
Indicators of RBE, rights to education, through Freire critical pedagogy	Students	3.43	-1.060	.330	Accept H ₀	Not significant
	Teachers/GA	3.39				
Indicators of RBE, rights in education, through Freire critical pedagogy	Students	3.49	20.147	.000	Reject H ₀	significant
	Teachers/GA	3.80				

Table 6 shows three variables under the RBE framework such as Indicators of RBE implementation, indicators of RBE, rights to education, through Freire critical pedagogy, and indicators of RBE, rights in education, through Freire critical pedagogy.

In terms of the indicators of RBE implementation, the weighted mean of teachers and guidance advocates with 3.73 was higher than the weighted mean obtained by the students which was 3.55. Since the computed p-value was .003 with a t-value of 4.320 was less than the standard level of significance, which was 0.05, therefore the null hypothesis that there was no significant difference on the indicators of RBE implementation as assessed by students and teachers/guidance advocates, was rejected. There was significant difference between the indicators of RBE framework implementation and Paulo Freire critical pedagogy. It implied that the RBE framework implementation in general did not conform to the philosophical lens of Paulo Freire critical pedagogy.

In terms of indicators of RBE, “rights to” education, through Freire critical pedagogy, the weighted mean of students with 3.43 was higher than the weighted mean obtained by the teachers and guidance advocates which was 3.39. Since the computed p-value was .330 with a t-value of -1.060 was higher than the standard level of significance, which was 0.05, therefore the null hypothesis that there was no significant difference on the indicators of RBE implementation as assessed by students and teachers/guidance advocates, was accepted. There was no significant difference between the indicators of RBE, “rights to” education and Paulo Freire critical pedagogy. It implied that the RBE framework implementation, “rights to” education conformed with the philosophical lens of Paulo Freire critical pedagogy as it was shown that the essence of education based on freedom was observed in schools, which was promoted by Freire in his pedagogy of freedom, i.e., giving man the ability to achieve his full potentials as human being through education. This also confirmed Freire’s idea that education must lead students to be active agents of their education which rejected the idea of practicing banking system in education, which based on the results was the lowest among the indicators in “rights to” education.

In terms of Indicators of RBE, “rights in” education, through Freire critical pedagogy, the weighted mean of teachers and guidance advocates with 3.80 was higher than the weighted mean obtained by the students which was 3.49. Since the computed p-value was .000 with a t-value of 20.147 was less than the standard level of significance, which was 0.05, therefore the null hypothesis that there was no significant difference on the Indicators of RBE, rights to education, through Freire critical pedagogy as assessed by students and

teachers/guidance advocates, was rejected. There was a significant difference between the indicators of RBE framework, “rights in” education and Paulo Freire critical pedagogy. It implied that the RBE framework, “rights in” education did not conform to the philosophical lens of Paulo Freire as manifested in the level of feelings of learners on their safety in school, and in the level of their motivation to engage in activities that promoted their well-being. Learners did not mention during interview that they did not feel safe in school, but with the result that they considered this indicator as the lowest, it implied that Paulo Freire’s pedagogical aim to achieve “humanization” was not achieved in schools.

Qualitative Interpretations of Results: Analysis of Interviews

To further validate the results obtained from the questionnaires used, the qualitative interpretation of data based on interviews conducted may substantiate the responses of the students and teachers/guidance advocates. This was used to obtain information on how they perceived and understood the content of the research. Results of the interviews were organized, and the following themes were formulated: Theme 1 stated that the research participants were not familiar with the existing RBE framework. Most of the answers of the student respondents indicated that they were not aware of the RBE framework. Even some of the teacher/guidance advocate respondents indicated that they were not aware of the RBE framework. Theme 2 stated accessibility of school facilities and inclusivity in education. Most of the student respondents focused on the opportunity they had of using the school facilities and equipment. Teachers on the other hand focused on mentioning their practice of welcoming all students in their schools regardless of status, gender preferences, religions and other factors that define diversity among learners. Theme 3 stated respect in various forms was promoted in school. All student respondents stated that their rights to be respected and rights to promote their well-being were observed in their schools. Similarly, teachers/guidance advocate respondents mentioned school programs that for them promote respecting learners’ rights.

Based on the interview, most of both students and teachers/guidance advocates admitted that they were not aware of the existing RBE framework. They may have ideas of their rights and duties to ensure that quality education is delivered, and that learners’ well-being must be promoted, but they were not very familiar with the DepEd Order on RBE framework. Some of them also mentioned that their idea of this framework also occurred while they were answering the survey questionnaire. On a positive note, the schools were remarkable in terms of promoting inclusivity in education and learners’ accessibility to school facilities. Both groups unanimously answered that their school provide them with facilities that were available and functional whenever they needed them. Those facilities according to them provided them with opportunity to improve their knowledge and skills. Teachers and guidance advocates highlighted in their responses that learners in their school were given equal opportunity to be enrolled in their schools regarded of their diversity. Lastly, the qualitative data also indicated that both groups were convinced that respect in any forms was promoted in their schools.

Summary and Conclusions

The summary and conclusions were drawn based on the findings of the study which highlighted the following: (1) Most student-respondents were grade 12 females, while most teacher/guidance advocate respondents were also females. As regards the work experience, the majority was 6-10 years, while 0-5 was the lowest. (2) The RBE framework implementation in public SHS providers in the Division of Biñan City was “moderately implemented”. The “rights to” education was overall quite higher than the “rights in” education. The highest indicator on the “rights to” education was “learners’ rights to education were promoted”, while the lowest indicator was “learners received quality education”. Whereas the highest indicator in the “rights in” education was “learners were being developed to become competent and job ready as well as active and responsible citizens”, while the lowest indicator was “learners felt respected in school, and that all school programs and activities ensured and promoted their well-being”. Other findings showed that the participants were not very familiar with the existing RBE framework and its corresponding DepEd Order 31, s. 2022 or Child Rights Policy: Adopting the Rights-Based Education Framework in Philippine Basic Education.

The indicators that the “rights to” education such as access to quality education are achieved based on Freire critical pedagogy was “moderately evident”. “The essence of education based on freedom was observed in schools” emerged as the highest indicator, while “banking system in education was still practiced in schools” was marked as the lowest indicator. The “rights to” education, particularly on Freire’s pedagogy of freedom was manifested. The indicators that the “rights in” education such as promotion of learner’s well-being are achieved based on Freire critical pedagogy was “moderately observable”. “All school programs and activities ensured learners’ good care and promoted their well-being”, emerged as the highest indicator, while “learners felt safe inside the classroom and within the school and were motivated to engage in activities that promote

their well-being” was marked as the lowest indicator. The teaching strategies employed by teachers promoted learners’ well-being, as well as the school programs and activities. The “rights in” education conforms to Freire’s critical pedagogy in so far as the highest indicator is concerned, however, having the feeling of safety inside the school and the motivation to engage in activities that promote students were rated as the lowest among indicators, in the lens of Freire’s critical pedagogy, this was not promoting “humanization”.

In terms of the indicators of RBE implementation, the null hypothesis was rejected, therefore, there was significant difference between the indicators of RBE framework implementation and Paulo Freire critical pedagogy. The RBE framework implementation in general did not conform to the philosophical lens of Paulo Freire critical pedagogy. In terms of indicators of RBE, “rights to” education, through Freire critical pedagogy, the null hypothesis was accepted, therefore, there was no significant difference between the indicators of RBE, “rights to” education and Paulo Freire critical pedagogy.

The RBE framework implementation, “rights to” education conformed with the philosophical lens of Paulo Freire critical pedagogy. In terms of indicators of RBE, “rights in” education, through Freire critical pedagogy, the null hypothesis was rejected therefore, there was a significant difference between the indicators of RBE framework, “rights in” education and Paulo Freire critical pedagogy. The RBE framework, “rights in” education did not conform to the philosophical lens of Paulo Freire critical pedagogy.

Based on the conclusions of the study, the following salient points were recommended for the sound RBE framework implementation. First, schools may enhance their delivery of quality education focusing on the teaching strategies and guidance program alignment with students’ needs. Second, schools may design programs that would promote learners’ well-being since learners indicated that respect was given to them.

Accessibility to quality education may be sustained while inclusivity in education may be enhanced providing schools with necessary facilities for diverse learning needs. Third, schools may supervise the teaching strategies and evaluation tools of teachers as it was indicated that banking system in education was still practiced in schools. Students may be encouraged to be active agents of their own education than mere recipients of information “deposited” by teachers during lectures and “withdrawn” during examinations.

Fourth, schools may continue to improve their programs to ensure that safety inside and outside school is observed, likewise, schools may provide engaging activities that would promote the well-being of learners. All schools may draft or review their student’s handbook to ensure that new provisions for rights to and rights in education are well defined and properly implemented in accordance with the mandate of DepEd Order 31, s., 2022 or Child Rights Policy: Adopting the Rights-Based Education Framework in Philippine Basic Education. Lastly, the future researchers may conduct study on the indicators of RBE framework implementation focusing on the gender issue to determine which has advantages and disadvantages in the implementation. It could be conducted in elementary or junior high school levels.

Declarations

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